

Samuel Beckett's *Waiting for Godot* and *Malone Dies*

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Abstract Samuel Beckett is a name to reckon with as far as modernism is concerned. He wrote a number of plays and is best known for his masterpiece *Waiting for Godot*. In his works there is no progressive narrative rather an epigrammatic style with powerful images that haunt one. He also wrote a number of novels in which he followed the same epigrammatic style. *Malone Dies* was written just before he started with *Waiting for Godot* and though it dealt with the same themes of futility of all human action, the emptiness of all human talk, the absolute void enveloping us from the beginning to the end and nothingness, the effect is much more pronounced in the play. A close look at both these works that focus on similar themes but use different medium, makes an interesting comparative study. Besides focusing on the same themes, both these works have a highly condensed style, yet the outcome is different and *Waiting for Godot* has come to stay for all times to come.

Keywords Waiting For Godot, Malone Dies, Absolute Void, Meaninglessness, Diseased Humanity, Vacuity, Boredom, Ennui, Condensed Style.

Introduction

Samuel Beckett best represents the spirit of modernism. In almost all his works, he orchestrates the existentialist philosophy laying emphasis on futility of all human action, the emptiness of all human talk, the absolute void enveloping us from the beginning to the end and nothingness. The portrayal of writhing, suffering and diseased humanity form the canvas of his work. Starting with fiction, he later turned to drama and brought alive the same themes of vacuity, boredom, ennui and meaninglessness on the stage with even more perfection.

Before writing his masterpiece *Waiting for Godot* in 1949, Beckett had already started with the Trilogy-*Molloy* (1947), *Malone Dies* (1948) and *The unnamable* (1949). *Waiting for Godot* was hence written immediately after *Malone Dies*. Both belonged to different genres that of drama and fiction respectively. A close look at both these works that focus on similar themes but use different medium, makes an interesting comparative study. Besides focusing on the same themes, both these works have a highly condensed style, yet the outcome is different and *Waiting for Godot* has come to stay for all times to come.

Objective of study The objective of this paper is to discuss about the Samuel Beckett's *Waiting for Godot* and *Malone Dies*.

Review of Literature

WFG opens with two tramps, Vladimir and Estragon waiting for someone called Godot, who is much talked about but never actually arrives. *Malone Dies* is the dying soliloquy of bed ridden Malone who is octogenarian and helpless. In both the protagonist(s) are waiting-Malone for his death and the tramps for Godot. The latter interestingly has been variously interpreted as God, death, hope, silence etc. but as Martin Esslin points out nevertheless 'waiting' as it is 'the central concern of the play'¹. In Act II Vladimir avers:

"We are...waiting for the night, waiting for Godot, waiting for...waiting."²

Main Text

Malone Dies opens with "I shall be quite dead in spite of all." Here is a typical Beckettian hero-old, wretched, impotent, lonely, confined both in body and mind and 'tired of breathing' (WG, p.76) wanting to die and waiting for death to arrive. In both the works, the basic issues tackled are the same-the search for self, the obsession with nothingness, absolute void, the static life, the rift between the mind and the body and absence of any action. In both time is eternal-yesterday, today and tomorrow is a continuous flow, in both death would be a welcome intrusion and a relief, in both uncertainties prevail and a kind of vacuum operates. However, the absurdity of void and the boredom of living is inoculated by defiant laughter in *Waiting for Godot* and this is conspicuous by its absence in *Malone Dies*.

Interestingly Vladimir and Estragon are Beckett's first protagonists who have the privilege of unrestricted use of limbs. All others suffer a restraint-they may be unable to move around, hence remain glued to a chair or be enclosed in urns, or maybe surrounded by a mound that keeps growing till they are almost buried in it. The same is true of his fiction. Murphy can move around but often likes to tie himself naked to a rocking chair, Watt is the gentle abused figure who 'moves like a broken doll'⁴. Molloy is crippled due to a stiff leg, Malone completely bed-ridden and the protagonist of *The Unnamable* has been reduced to a worm.

Malone Dies speaks of a world that is 'dead, airless and waterless' (MD, p.34) and this is the world Beckett brings on the stage in *Waiting for Godot*, 'a barren tree and a country road' (WG, p. 7) . Existing in such a dead, airless and a dry world is itself a sin and Malone relating the story of Macmann realises that 'Whatever the sin is ...living in not sufficient atonement for it or that this atonement was itself a sin calling for more atonement.' (MD, p.41). In *Waiting for Godot* when Vladimir suggests, "Suppose we repented?" Estragon retorts, "Repented what... Our being born?" (WG, p.11)

Vladimirs, Estragons and Malones are never able to forgive their parents for bringing them in the world and making them carry their crosses. They are caught in what Camus describes as 'the unspeakable penalty, where the whole being is exerted towards accomplishing nothing.'⁵ Beckett once said that he liked the statement of St. Augustine that stated:

Do not despair; one of the thieves was saved.

Do not presume; one of the thieves was damned.⁶

This theme of the two thieves on the cross, the arbitrariness of the bestowal of grace, finds voice in both the texts. Malone consoles himself with the assurance, "Why be discouraged? one of the thieves was saved, that is a generous percentage." (MD, p.72) and in the play Vladimir voices the same sentiment, "...Two thieves, crucified at the same time as our saviour one...one is supposed to have been saved and the other... damned." (WG, p.12)

However what begins in hope ends in despair with Vladimir questioning the authenticity of the four versions available and Estragon concluding, "People are bloody ignorant apes" (WG, p.13). Pozzo in *Waiting for Godot* also wants to get rid of Lucky his companion so as to make the fifty percent chance his own. Ruby Cohen comments:

The two thieves are Didi and Gogo, the two thieves are Pozzo and Lucky, the two thieves are you and me and the play is shaped to reflect that fearful symmetry.⁷

God in both the works is referred to as omnipotent, mysterious but cruel, a power that holds the strings and plays with them. Malone rues that we are at the mercy or "behest of one of the powers that be" (MD, p.9) and there's a kind of search to establish a "relation between that which suffers and that which causes to suffer" (MD, p.85), though the search like the waiting is futile.

Godot on his part is also illogical and irrational arbiter of punishments or rewards. He loves the boy who minds the sheep and hates the one who minds the goats and the boy cannot justify why he does so. The waiting likewise is marked by an ambivalence-salvation and damnation alternating. Lucky's words (the only ones he speaks before turning dumb) talk of a God who from "the heights of divine apathia, divine athambia loves us dearly with some exception for reason unknown..." (WG, p.43) And in the novel the horror of the whole existence is aptly brought out by the protagonist:

I shall try and make a little creature in my image, no matter what I say. And seeing what a poor thing I have made or how like myself I shall eat it. Then be alone for a long time not knowing what my prayer shall be nor to whom. (MD, p.65)

The dominant theme in both the works remain the dominance of nothingness. "Nothing is more real than nothing" Beckett emphasizes in *Malone Dies* and the play too in its very opening dialogue proclaims: "Nothing to be done" (WG, p.9) The strain regularly keeps resounding with sentences such as "What do we do?"(WG,p.67), "I hear nothing"(WG, p.19), "I see nothing"(WG,p.25), "I know nothing" (WG, P.69). Even the messenger in the IInd act when asked as to what Godot does declares, "He does nothing" (WG, p.91). It seems the saviour himself is caught in this void of nothingness and is perhaps as helpless. Refrains of nothing emit the odor of death and decay. Change, movement and flux are the axial dynamics of health, life and vitality. But Malone like Vladimir and Estragon is static in time and space, hence the repulsive odor remains.

Another common feature in both is the marked rift between the mind and the body. Vladimir is all mind and Estragon all body and Malone's "body does not make up its mind" (MD, p.29) and in another scene from the novel Malone cannot summon his legs at will as they are leagues away. Similarly, the language seems to make no sense in both the works and virtues like pity and compassion are extinct in both. Everyone turns a blind eye to the suffering of the other. Vladimir cannot comprehend where Estragon's shoe pinches or even if it does. "It hurts?" (WG, P.10) he asks him and immediately afterwards blurts out, "No one suffers but you" (WG, p.10) Estragon on his part is blind to see the running sore on Lucky's neck. Ironically the empathy that pops up when Estragon proffers his handkerchief to Lucky is annihilated by the terrible kick he gets in return, that sends him off howling in pain and Pozzo comes out with the terse, heartless comment:

The tears of the world are a constant quantity. For each one who begins to weep somewhere else another stops. (WG, p.33)

Having finished the novel *Malone Dies* in 1948, Beckett started working on the play with the same themes but different medium. He had perfected a terse style in *Malone Dies*, it being a monologue of a dying person. The language here is the language of the mind and the style matches the subject. It ends with:

...he will not hit anyone any more, he will not touch anyone any more, either with it or with it or with it or

... ..

Or with his pencil or with his stick or

light light I mean

never there he will never

never anything

there

anymore (MD, p.144)

This style was carried forward in the play with greater precision, intensity and impact. Spoken words exert great impact in drama especially when silence becomes a language as it does in *Waiting for Godot*. These silences help the effect sink in. Also many a times whatever is said is unsaid in the stage directions. "*Silence. No one moves*" nullifies the effect of "Adieu." In his novel *The Dream of Fair to Middling Women* (1932) Beckett had clarified: "The experience of my readers shall be between the phrases in the silence communicated by the interval..."⁸

A play presents one with a visual experience that is unmatched. No amount of words could convey the horror of cruelty that a human can inflict on another which is conveyed by a single powerful image of Lucky appearing on the stage with a running sore caused by the rope around his neck. Such images combine with dialogues to jolt the reader and sensitizes him to the absurdity of his condition

Conclusion

Malone Dies closes with an enviable calm drifting over Malone and a weird haunting peace. The search of the tramps on the other hand continues. They are damned into this cycle of waiting day in and day out. Their situation is actually quite accurately summed up by Malone:

...he who has waited long enough will wait forever. And there comes an hour when nothing more can happen and nobody more can come and all is ended but the waiting that knows itself in vain...you have been waiting too long, you are no longer sufficiently alive to be able to stop. (MD, p.84)

Thus *Waiting for Godot* presents with even greater force and intensity than *Malone Dies* the images of futility of existence, the void and the nothingness. Drama has the freshness, the precision and intensity deriving largely from its visual aspects that fiction as a genre lacks.

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3. Samuel Beckett, *Malone Dies* (London: Penguin Books, 1951), p.5. All subsequent quotations are taken from this edition and have been incorporated in the text, abbreviated as *MD*.
4. A. Alvarez, *Beckett* (Great Britain: Win Collins sons & Co. Ltd., 1973) p. 38.
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10. A. Alvarez, *Beckett* (Great Britain: Win Collins sons & Co. Ltd., 1973) p. 59.